

CONCILIARE: Pioneering Research into Transformations of Colonial Cultural Heritage Across Europe

The CONCILIARE project (*Confidently Changing colonial heritage*), funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (RIA), is set to redefine the way European societies engage with colonial cultural heritage (CCH). This groundbreaking initiative brings together a consortium of leading universities and research institutions from six European countries—Belgium, the Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Finland, and Croatia—to map, analyze and advance the transformation of colonial heritage in contemporary public discourse.

The **University of Coimbra** (Portugal) coordinates the project, working alongside the following institutions:

- **Belgium:** *Université Libre de Bruxelles; CegeSoma – Centre d’Étude Guerre et Société; Afropean Project*
- **The Netherlands:** *Utrecht University*
- **Portugal:** *CECS - University of Minho; CES – University of Coimbra*
- **Italy:** *La Sapienza University of Rome*
- **Finland:** *University of Helsinki*
- **Croatia:** *Ivo Pilar Institute for Social Sciences; Afropean Project*
- *International Council of Museums*

External experts participating in the project include scholars from the following institutions:

- **Switzerland:** *University of Basel*
- **Democratic Republic of the Congo:** *University of Kinshasa*
- **Germany:** *Center for Anthropological Research on Museums and Heritage*
- **United States:** *Barry College and Rutgers University*
- **Belgium:** *Catholic University of Louvain*
- **Spain:** *Autonomous University of Madrid*
- **United Kingdom:** *Museums Association, University of York, University of Salford*

A European Approach to Decolonizing Cultural Narratives

Running from March 1st, 2024, to February 28th 2027, CONCILIARE seeks to analyze ongoing transformations in colonial cultural heritage across four key domains:

1. **Textbooks** – How the colonial past is represented, through text and images, in educational materials.
2. **Public Spaces** – The presence and salience of colonial heritage in urban landscapes, as monuments and street names.
3. **Museums** – The narratives, curatorial practices and interpretation of colonial-era artifacts.
4. **Cultural Consumption** – The lingering influence of colonial in everyday cultural products.

By examining institutional policies, media narratives, and public responses, the project aims to provide an evidence-based framework to promote confidence in the changes of the PCC, and intercultural dialogue.

Next Events

CONCILIARE team is currently organizing its **Annual Meeting 2025**, which will take place on March 19th-20th at the Institute of Social Sciences Ivo Pilar in Zagreb, Croatia. The event will feature a plenary session discussing the results, challenges, and future activities of the project, as well as Individual WP Meetings, the General Assembly, and the Executive Board Meeting.

Another crucial event in the CONCILIARE agenda is **(De)Colonial Visions: Dialogues in Visual Culture, Alterities, and Artivisms** – a joint event by CONCILIARE, MigraMediaActs, and the SOPCOM Visual Culture Working Group. This one-day event, taking place in Braga on the 28th of April, and held in Portuguese and English, will bring together scholars, artists, and activists to foster critical conversations about the colonial past and its enduring impact on contemporary society. The event will be in a hybrid format, with in-person and online participation options available.

For more information, visit the project's official website: conciliare.eu

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